

HIV SITUATION IN BICOL REGION: LIVED EXPERIENCES OF PERSONS LIVING WITH HIV AMID PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

On March 16, 2020, a Luzon-wide enhanced community quarantine (ECQ) was imposed, restricting people's movement to control the spread of COVID-19. Unknown to many, while the walls to keep most people safe, a certain population group were barred access to life saving medications. These are the persons living with HIV (PLHIV). The study is focused on exploring the lived experiences of PLHIVs and to develop recommendations to be able to immediately respond to their situations in the middle of thinning down health system, impacted by the pandemic. Specifically, to find answers to: what is the situation of PLHIVs; what are the challenges faced by PLHIVs; what the coping mechanisms of the PLHIVs are, and; what possible measures can be derived from their experiences. This is qualitative research which looked into the lived experiences of eight PLHIVs in Bicol region, through one-on-one interview. Two key informant interviews and the review of related literatures was done to support the experiences. Ultimately, the experiences of the participants were used to draw recommendations in improving HIV programming and services amid pandemic, using ecological models in public health. The study revealed that: most PHLIVs live outside the area where their treatment hubs are located, and that with forced border restrictions imposed, accessing live saving medications is impossible; more than the COVID-19, PLHIVs' mental health were more affected by the having no access to their anti-retroviral medications; most of PLHIVs were laid off from their source of income, and; some PLHIVs were locked down in locations outside their actual residences. With very few functional treatment hubs in the Bicol region, PLHIVs coped in their recent situation through: family and community support provided emotional and psychological comfort; community-based groups providing assistance to PLHIVs were supportive in bridging gaps in the HIV programming and services. It is highly recommended to strengthen the ecological elements around the PLHIVs in particular along intrapersonal, interpersonal, institutional and public policy levels. Series of online educational discussions to mental health and HIV situation can be done to influence PLHIVs' intrapersonal and interpersonal response to their social and health situation. Equally important is for community-based groups and local governments, including national agencies, to enact healthy public programs and policies which can promote or constrain behaviors, likewise, support health actions to respond to the thinning down public HIV programs, as most health programs shifted to COVID-19 response.

Key words: Persons Living with HIV, SRHR, Covid-19 and HIV, sexual health

Introduction

Due to COVID-19 alarming rate of cross infection, most societies in the world are threatened and the lives of millions of people changed dramatically. In the Philippines, it was March 16, 2020 when the national government imposed a mandatory Luzon-wide lockdown as a response to the threats of the COVID-19 pandemic. While it was in midnight of March 17, 2020 when the community quarantine was raised to 'enhanced community quarantine'. In a report by Rappler, the heightened community quarantine also brings a heightened presence of uniformed personnel to enforce the strict quarantine measures across 8 regions, including the National Capital Region and some other regions outside Luzon (Tomacruz 2020).

The main purpose of the community quarantine is to ensure the safety of the public and to prevent the spread of the COVID-19. However, this wall to protect the public and keep them safe, served as a wall keeping a certain population group from accessing their life-saving anti-retroviral medications – the People Living with HIV (PLHIV) population. PLHIVs are immunocompromised individuals who rely on the anti-retroviral medications which is part of their Antiretroviral Treatment (ART). ART is very important part of PLHIVs daily lives. ART reduces the amount of HIV in the person's blood, keeps them healthy and prevents illness (HIV.gov 2019).

Putting the lives and health needs of PLHIVs in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic and the imposed enhanced community quarantine, DOH records show that there are 45,143 PLHIVs enrolled in HIV Antiretroviral Treatment (NHSSS 2020). This means, that there are 45,143 people who will be restricted from travelling to access their ART medications from their health stations or treatment hubs. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), countries need to make difficult decisions to balance the demands of responding directly to COVID-19, while simultaneously engaging in strategic planning and coordinated action to maintain essential health service delivery, mitigating the risk of

system collapse (WHO 2020). However, as every nation tries to face the COVID-19, health systems thinned down. The Philippines health system was no exception. As the country's state of COVID-19 continue to worsen, the health system dwindled. As more basic health services and programming were shifted to COVID-19 response, the sexual health and HIV programming and services were severely affected.

Rationale

Region V or Bicol region is part of the geo-political areas included in the Luzon-wide enhanced community quarantine. It is a home to over 1,000 PLHIVs and 761 PLHIVs enrolled in ART (DOH CHD Bicol 2019). Bicol region is composed of six provinces. Four of which are part of the mainland Luzon: Camarines Norte, Camarines Sur, Albay and Sorsogon. While two others are the island provinces of Catanduanes and Masabate. There are only two HIV treatment hubs in the region: Bicol Medical Center located in Naga City, Camarines Sur, and Bicol Regional Training and Teaching Hospital located in Legazpi City, Albay (DOH 2018).

As a researcher and a public health practitioner, sexual and reproductive health is at the core of professional practice. Together with a number of friends, we started a community-based organization in the Bicol Region which is based in Daraga, Albay, but operations extend throughout the region and other areas where there are Bicolanos needing help along the lines of sexual health and HIV. Working along these lines of public health for more than a decade, the researcher is fully aware of potential impact to the lives of PLHIVs as the government responds to the threats of COVID-19, such as the imposed community quarantine and shift of health services to COVID-19 response.

PLHIVs are individuals whose immune system are compromised. While their ART medications are essentially part of their everyday life to keep their viral load low, hence, improving their immune system. These ART medications are usually being resupplied on a monthly basis by the treatment hub where the

PLHIV client is being treated. With the travel restrictions and risks of acquiring COVID-19 puts the entire PLHIV community at a very disadvantageous and unhealthy position. Hence, this study is both important and urgent.

Current State of Research in the Field

According to International Perspective on Sexual and Reproductive Health, sexual and reproductive health will also be affected by societal responses to the pandemic, such as local or national lockdowns that force health services to shut down if they are not deemed essential, as well as the consequences of physical distancing, travel restrictions and economic slowdowns (Riley T., Sully E., Ahmed Z., and Biddlecom A. 2020).

Even before the pandemic, HIV/AIDS services and programming has been lacking. Current country efforts have been insufficient to reach targets on testing, diagnosis, and antiretroviral therapy initiation and that the HIV situation of country reflects the need to have an increased resource allocation and programmatic enhancements, however, civil society organizations can provide support to bridge gaps in government HIV programming and services (DOH 2016 and UNAIDS 2020).

At this stage of the pandemic, we are yet to see the impact of COVID-19 protocols such as travel restrictions, lockdowns, and shift of health human resources to COVID-19 response. However, this is the right time to look into the lived experiences of PLHIVs to be able to understand further their situation and context amid pandemic. Ultimately, to develop possible measures to be recommended in improving the state of HIV programs and access of PLHIVs to such services in the Bicol region and other parts of the country.

Synthesis of the Art

Globally, rate of new HIV infection has declined. However, among the four countries with highest rate of new cases is the Philippines with an average of 31-35 new cases daily (UNAIDS 2019 and NHSS 2020).

The Philippines among very few countries in the world with a worsening state of HIV/AIDS as evidenced by high rates of new HIV cases in the past five years - national education on effective HIV prevention methods is nonexistent, and laws prohibit condom access and HIV testing to people for minors without parental consent, and these are factors contributing to the worsening epidemic among young persons in the country (Human Rights Watch 2016).

ART is a combination of antiretroviral drugs and other medications to prevent and treat the many opportunistic infections that a PLHIV may manifest when the immune system becomes compromised due to HIV (UNAIDS 2016 and WHO 2015).

In the majority (94%) of countries responding, ministry of health staff working in the area of NCDs were partially or fully reassigned to support COVID-19 (WHO 2020).

When communities organize and people empower each other, oppression can be replaced by rights and access to HIV services can be accelerated. Peer-to-peer counsellors, community health workers, door-to-door service providers, grass-root activists and networks of people living with or affected by HIV all have key roles to play in the response to HIV. As this report shows, community leadership in the AIDS response helps to ensure that HIV services are relevant to, and reach, the people who need them the most (UNAIDS 2019).

CSOs and community-based organizations (CBOs) play a pivotal role in reshaping the HIV programming in communities affected by the pandemic (UNAIDS 2020). However, the implementation of community quarantine measures in most parts of the country resulted to restrictions on transportation services to individuals performing essential functions, like CBO staff and volunteers who perform HIV services provision. Travel restrictions and physical distancing measures in the Philippines have also disrupted the supply and distribution of essential ART medications, which may decrease adherence to treatment (Quintalang M.I., Bermudez A., and Operario D. 2020).

According to UNICEF and the WHO,

community-based health care is an essential part of primary care at all times; in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, the distinct capacity of trusted community members for social engagement and delivering care where it is needed is ever more critical (WHO 2020).

Research Gap

Existing literatures and studies showed relatedness to this present study, which are along the lines of HIV/AIDS and COVID-19 pandemic. However, this study is specifically knitted to look into lived experiences of PLHIVs and to provide possible recommendations to immediately address urgent and important needs of this population group. No same study has been conducted in Bicol region.

Objectives of the Study

The study is focused on exploring the lived experiences of PLHIVs whose lives were impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic, and to draw possible recommendations to be able to immediately respond to their situations in the middle of thinning down health system, impacted by the pandemic. Specifically, to find answers to:

What is the situation of PLHIVs in Bicol Region?

What are the challenges faced by PLHIVs?

What are the coping/adaptation measures or mechanisms of the PLHIVs? And;

What possible measures/recommendations can be drawn from their experiences?

Theory

This study adapted McLeroy's and colleagues' ecological model for health promotion, which is often used in public health. By adapting this model, information from the participants to the study were analyzed to draw sound recommendations in improving the situation of PLHIVs in Bicol region. For the purpose of this study, analysis was factored in four levels: intrapersonal, interpersonal, community and public policy.

Intrapersonal factors include characteristics of the individual such as knowledge, attitudes, behavior, self-concept and skills. Interpersonal are formal and informal social network and social support system. Community factors refers to relationships among organizations, institutions, and informal groups and networks within defined boundaries. And public policy refers to institution, local, and regional, even national level laws and policies.

Methodology

This study used qualitative research. This is an exploratory phenomenological inquiry to look into the lived experiences of eight PLHIVs in Bicol region amid pandemic. One-on-one interview was done to gather information from the participants of the study, in particular, to look into their perceptions, perspectives and understanding of their current situation amid pandemic. This study used existing information about HIV programs and services from key informants (KI) from government institutions and CSO with HIV initiatives in the region. The information essential to understanding the PLHIV situation in a community level include: existing mechanisms for PLHIVs; existing programs or policies; and how these mechanisms, programs and policies are being implemented and accessed by PLHIVs. Other vital information in this investigation are the challenges encountered by PLHIVs, their coping measures and mechanisms to meet their health needs, and; most importantly, the promising experiences which can be translated into points of recommendations for actions.

The information needed in this study were generated through conduct of one-on-one interviews with eight PLHIV participants and two KIs using online means. The key informant interviews and the review of related literatures were utilized to support the experiences drawn from the PLHIV participants in the study. Ultimately, the experiences of the participants were used to draw recommendations in improving HIV programming and services amid pandemic, using ecological models in public health.

Due to urgency of the subject of the study, and the level of sensitivity involving the participants, purposive sampling was utilized in identifying the eight PLHIV participants, and two key informants. The PLHIV participants were preselected according to a set of criteria – enrolled in ART program, a resident of any city or town in Bicol region, and is willing to volunteer and be part of the study. While key informants were pre-determined according to a set of criteria – a person of authority and experience, either from public or private, involved in HIV programs and service provision.

Letters of intent to conduct the study were sent to involved institutions prior to the conduct of the study. Likewise, an assistance from a private HIV support group were requested to send invitations to potential and willing PLHIV participants to the study. Pursuant to Republic Act No. 10173 or Data Privacy Act, and Republic Act No. 11166 or Philippine HIV and AIDS Policy Act, the purpose of the study were comprehensively explained to the participants, and that informed consent was explained and acquired. Privacy and confidentiality of every participant to the study were upheld with utmost importance.

A question guide was prepared and used during data gathering. Online one-on-one interviews were recorded. Coding was utilized in treating the participants in the study. The information collected was categorized and thematized. Ultimately, the researcher utilized the results of the study to interpret the experiences and to identify gaps, and adapted ecological model in public health to come up with measures to be recommended to improving HIV programs and services amid pandemic.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Results

Situation of the PLHIV in Bicol Region

About the Participants. The participants and key informants to the study were coded accordingly – Pax A to H refers to the PLHIV participants, while KI 1 to 3 refers to the key informants. The PLHIV participants to the study were intentionally to be presented with no specific details which may directly or indirectly result to them being identified. Below is essential information to provide context to each participant:

Pax A. 34 y/o female. A mother to 3 children and breastfeeding mom to her youngest child. She is from the island province of Masbate.

Pax B. 19 y/o male. A working student. He is from coastal municipality southern part of Sorsogon Province.

Pax C. 30 y/o male. Laid off from work due to pulmonary tuberculosis. He is from a town 2 hours drive away to Naga City.

Pax D. 41 y/o male. Manages his own food business. He is from an urban village in the Province of Sorsogon.

Pax E. 23 y/o male. She is a transwoman and works in a beauty salon in a coastal town in

Sorsogon Province.

Pax F. 26 y/o male. He lives alone in a boarding house 1 hour drive away from Naga City. He works as a service crew in a food business.

Pax G. 20 y/o male. A student locked down in his boarding house in Legazpi City. He is originally from Masbate.

Pax H. 22 y/o male. Stranded in Laguna with his relatives. He is being treated in treatment hub located in Legazpi City.

KI 1. A public health nurse and focal person of Local AIDS and HIV programs of the Province of Albay

KI 2. President of GM Bicol for Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights, Inc. An NGO providing PLHIV support and provides HIV services in the region

Access of PLHIVs to HIV programs. All participants shared that means of getting HIV services is to go directly to their respective treatment hubs. While most participants shared that they also get services from CSO groups, but major services, such as getting their medications, treatment and other laboratory requirements are only offered in treatment hubs like BRTTH and BMC. Social services however, according to two participants, can be accessed from the LGUs of their residence. In the present time of COVID-19, their link to their usual point of services are through text messaging and online means.

Pax E. "...sa BRRTH po ako nag kukuwa arvs ko. Pati ang pagpacheck up duman na man po."

(I get my medications and do my regular checks at BRRTH)

Pax B. "kapag may gusto po ako maaraman, dakulang tabang man po si GM bicol kasi makaskas mag simbag sa messenger... minsan po mas nag sisimbag pa GM kesa su nurse sa hub"

(If I need information, I usually contact GM Bicol through messenger. They respond quicker than the nurse in charge at the hub.)

Pax G. "kapag may gusto po ako

maaraman, dakulang tabang man po si GM bicol kasi makaskas mag simbag sa messenger... minsan po mas nag sisimbag pa GM kesa su nurse sa hub"

(If I need information, I usually contact GM Bicol through messenger. They respond quicker than the nurse in charge at the hub.)

Pax A. "...nakakahagad man tabang sa social welfare ki dikit na ayuda pang pamasahang pasiriling sa legazpi, minsan panbulong... dakulang tabang man su PWD ID nakaua ko sa munispyo."

(Assistance for transportation and medicines can be sought from the local social welfare office... the PWD ID was also helpful issued by the municipal office.)

KI 1. "sa treatment hub lang talaga makakakuha ng ARV med refills. Sa LGUs may mga HIV focal din, pero bako man gabos na LGU may social hygiene clinics. Arog sa Albay, diit man sana may SHC like sa Legazpi city, sa Daraga ayu man."

(Only treatment hubs provide arv meds refills. While LGUs are supposed to have HIV focal, but not all LGUs have social hygiene clinics. Like in Albay, there is SHC in Legazpi City, and Daraga got one too.)

KI 2. "often, ang mga local AIDS council kan LGUs part na pirmi ang social welfare office. In fact, dakol sa mga LGU partners ta na may makusog na programa ang mswdo sa HIV."

(Local AIDS council membership often includes the local social welfare office. In fact, most of our LGU partners, their MSWDO has strong support to HIV programs)

Living and health conditions of the PLHIVs. Most participants have health concerns in relation to the HIV status. Most participants require access to their HIV medications and other related treatment for the current opportunistic infections. While few

participants complained about being laid off from work or barred from their socio-economic activities to support their daily needs. One participant pointed out being alone in his residence, which is a boarding house, as he was caught by the imposed community quarantine. Despite need to access basic health services such as medical checks, and other sexual and reproductive health services, laboratory diagnostics – these services aren't available due to temporary shift of services to COVID-19 response.

Pax C. "...suya man sa pandemic ta apektado means magkaincome... nagpapabulong ako tulong bulan na sa TB dots sa Naga. May labs dapat ako last week, pero dai man nagibo ta lockdown na ngani."

(it's unfortunate that the pandemic took away our opportunity to earn money... I am under TB treatment in TB DOTS in Naga, in fact I was supposed to run some labs but wasn't able to do it due to lockdown.)

Pax D. "mao na an resulta san covid kay maluya na talaga kita ta... main source ko sin income an pagluto-luto man hamok"

(it's expected to earn less from food business because of COVID... it is my main source of income)

Pax E. "close na muna su salon dahil sa pandemic. Mao man hak pati gin aasahan ko pambakal sin bulong ko. Diri man ako maka rani kara mama kay kun haputon ako nano an sakit ko, diri ko man masimbag... nahadok man ako magsabi"

(The salon where I work closed due to pandemic. It's my sole source of money to be able to buy myself my medications. I cannot ask help from my mother because I am afraid that if I am asked about my health condition, I am very afraid to tell them about it.)

KI 2. "madami tayo natatanggap na chat message especially from PLHIV brothers and sisters asking for financial assistance. Dahil sa pandemic, lahat naman affected, pero most of our PLHIVs in Bicol are self-

reliant and very few are open to their family about their status."

(We have been receiving chat messages especially from PLHIV brothers and sisters asking for financial assistance. Because of the pandemic, its understandable that many are affected, but our PLHIVs in Bicol are self-reliant and very few are open to their family about their status.)

KI 2. "...madami din tayo nakukuha na request for assistance na need nila magpagamot, mag undergo laboratory, in fact, we have two PLHIVs under our support arm na nasa hospital now na needs blood donors, which napakahirap mahanap dahil sa pandemic."

(there are many requests for assistance for medications, for laboratory, and we have two PLHIVs under our support arm which are hospitalized who needs blood donors. Blood donors are very hard to get due to pandemic.)

KI 1. "sui bang mga RH services, da wa su mga social hygiene clinics and birthing facilities, na divert muna temporarily to covid"

(Some RH services like social hygiene and birthing facilities were temporarily shifted to covid)

"even ang ibang social services natin, naka focus muna sa covid..."

(even some of social services where made to focus to covid)

Physical location of PLHIVs. Most participants shared that they are more than one hour ride, in a regular commute, to their nearest HIV facility. While one participant pointed out that it would require them to assign two to three days when going to the treatment hub. Another participant explained that due to travel restrictions which resulted to being lockdown outside Bicol region, he is approximately 10 hours away from his regular hub.

Pax B. "usually bakun man dipisil pasiring sa brt, haluy na an sad na oras"

(Usually it is not a hassle going to BRTTH, one or less than one hour travel.)

“...kaya lan na tyempo nangad na anion ako sa Laguna ka mama kan nag lockdown, sabihon ta na 10- 12 oras pauli samo”

(...but, it so unfortunate that the lockdown caught me while I am in Laguna, so it would be like 10-12 hours trip going back home.)

Pax A. “minsan kaiba ko mga aki ko, nag spend kami duwa o tulong aldaw kun mapasiring ako sa legazpi. Byahe tapos tawid dagat pa sana, sarong aldaw na ubos mo”

(Sometimes, I go to Legazpi with my child and we spend 2 to 3 days for that trip. Land trip and travel by sea, those alone would cost a day of our time)

KI 2. “base sa PHLHIV community na pig assist ta, actually more than half sainda medyo hararayo talaga ang istaran.”

(based on the PLHIV community we are helping, more than half of them reside from far communities).

Challenges faced by the PLHIVs in Bicol Region

Access to HIV medicines severely impacted. All participants shared their concerns about getting their regular supply of ART. The imposed community quarantine striped them the opportunity to do their usual travel from their residence to their treatment hubs to resupply their ART medications. While one participant is seriously concerned about his medication which can only cover three more days. One participant

Pax A. "Duwang oras na byahe pa ako pa-port. Nagbabarko pa ako pa-Donsol, tapos UV pa Daraga. Kada bulan nagbayahe ako pa BRTTH (referring to Bicol Regional Training and Teaching Hospital) para lang sa ARVs ko. Makatakot na maray na may ECQ ta paano na ako kaini..."

(I am travelling two hours to the nearest port, and requires a boat ride to Donsol. From there, I need to travel again by UV (referring to public van transport) to Daraga. Every month, I need to go to BRTTH to get my refills. I am worried, with ECQ, I don't know what will happen to me...)

Pax B. "Sa BRT (referring to Bicol Regional Training and Teaching Hospital) pa treatment hub ko. Sa totoo lang, may kaka-refill ko lang, pero pano ka kun mataod taod pa ini na lockdown..."

(My treatment hub is in BRT. I just got my refill, but what will happen to me if this lockdown will be extended...)

Pax E. "nasabutan ko man na dahil sa hiv mababa lang resistensya ko. Kaya pasigurado pirmi kun maluwat tapos diri magpararabas lalo na sa matawuhon, kaya afraid man magpa-legazpi maski wara na lockdown"

(I understand that because of HIV I have a weaker immune system. I make sure that I fully equipped every time I go outside and avoid going to crowded places. I am also afraid on travelling to Legazpi even if

lockdown is over.)

Pax F. "Mayo na ako bulong, tulo na sana ini. Ma' man pati masakyan na pasiring sa Naga..."

(I am running out of meds, I only got here meds for the next three days. There is no way for me to travel to Naga)

KI 2. "...actually, duwa man sana kaya ang treatment hub sa Bicol. BMC sa Cam Sur, BRT sa Albay. Ang PHO kang Masbate, newly designated na sya na treatment hub."

(There are two treatment hubs in Bicol. BMC (Bicol Medical Center) in Camarines sur and BRT in Albay. However, the Provincial Health Office of Masbate has recently been designated as a treatment hub.)

Distance to service providers and facilities. Most participants shared that they are quite far from HIV services and facilities. While one participant is relatively near, however, would still require to commute to reach the nearest facility to him. Another participant who is in a special predicament shared that he happens to be locked down in a place outside Bicol region, while his treatment hub is in the Province of Albay. There are also other PLHIVs who were displaced by the ECQ and due to distance to their treatment hubs, had concerns about getting refills of their HIV medicines.

Pax A. "...an byahe haling Masbate pa Donsol 3-4 na oras kumporme sa panahon. May fast craft man ma duwang oras sana... idagdag mo pa su land travel..."

(...travel by sea from Masbate to Donsol takes about 3-4 hours and depends on how is the weather. There is an option to take fast-craft which may take around 2 hours. However, there is still land travel...)

Pax G. "sa Legazpi man sana ako, sarong jeep sana pa BRT minsan tricycle pa city health..."

(I'm staying in Legazpi and I am one jeepney ride to BRT, and sometimes I take a tricycle to city health...)

Pax H. "Yaon ako kara mama sa Laguna. Didi na ako nawbutan kan ECQ... kaya problema ko talaga pawno' ako nakuku ki refill ko sa BRT."

(I'm visiting my mother in Laguna, and ECQ caught me here... now I am concerned about how to get my refill from BRT.)

KI 1. "Madami talaga ang clients na ganyan ang situation. Meron pa nga ibang clients na PLHIVs na nasa Bicol either work or vacation, tapos dito sa Bicol na abutan ng lockdown."

KI 2. "Nakaka-receive kita actually SOS from other groups outside sa Bicol na ang ibang members ninda or clients ninda na trap ng lockdown sa Bicol, tapos nag susubli ki meds para lang ma sustain su medication..."

Anxiety related to COVID-19 threats. All participants expressed their concerns about how threatening COVID-19 is to their already immunocompromised situation. Most of the participants shared about that it's unimaginable to their present health condition if ever they caught COVID-19 infection. Most participants associated their knowledge about COVID-19 to the news they've watched from the news and videos posted on social media, likewise, other materials about COVID-19 they've seen posted on social media.

Pax A. "makatakuton man talaga ang covid. Ako natatakot ako para samuya, sa news baga pigsasabi sa ibang bansa dakulon na nagadan dahil sa covid"

(Covid is really scary. Personally, I am afraid for my family, especially that in the news, they are reporting many deaths due to covid)

Pax F. "makatakot ta bagsak po baga immune system mi. ako ngani po kung

bako man kaipuhan dai na ako nagpaparaluwas... pirmi lang ako sa bhaus"

(our immune system is compromised and it makes me really scared. If it is not important, I would choose not to go outside my house)

Pax H. "di man maiwasan nasusugo magluwas magbakal, everytime yaon ako sa luwas pigiisip ko nahawaan na ako. Dakul baka sa FB mga videos tapos story na su iba ngani nagtuturumba na lang bugla."

(its unavoidable if I am asked to go run errands, like buying something outside. Every time I go outside, I somewhat feel I am infected already. So many terrifying stories on FB, some you'll see people just drops down.)

KI 1. "Panic talaga ang mga tawo lalo na kung naiilind ninda na dakol ang apektado. Minsan dakol man kami nagging patients na kadakol ki maling akala."

(People panic because of the news and reports they hear, in fact, we even have clients that know lots of misconceptions about covid)

Stress related to financial problems and food supply. All participants expressed feeling of some extent of getting stressed along in terms of financial stability and food supply in the middle of community quarantine. Some participants particularly expressed getting stressed about budget for getting medications. All participants shared that they have received food assistance from the local authorities, however, some of the participants expressed concerns that the food assistance

isn't enough throughout the duration of lockdown, when they have been cut off from going to work as well.

Pax D. "nakakua man kami payuda didi hali sa barangay tapos sa munisipyo"

(we did receive food packages from the village local authority and the municipal government)

Pax E. "...pasalamat ta may ayuda, pero sa harong kaya ako man sana talaga ang may fix na income, kaya medyo hadit na baka kukulangon ini sa kahaluyan kan lockdown. Sige po baga ka extend makastress much"

(...thankful that we received food assistance, but since I am actually the only one in my home that has fix income, I am stressed that the lockdown keeps on getting extended)

Pax C. "sana lang may ayuda man para sa nangangaipo ki pambakal bulong. Sa totoo lang makakapay isipon na ipambabakal mi na sana pagkakan, pero nagkikipit pa si mama makabakal sana bulongko." (I really hope there would also be some assistance for those who need to buy medicines. I feel stressed enough that my mother would have to use our budget for food just to get me medicines.)

Coping/adaptation measures or mechanisms of PLHIVs

A number of activities were shared by the participants on how they try to adapt to the new normal, including to the stress and anxiety the pandemic caused. At the **individual level**, all participants shared that they hold on to prayers and that their faith to 'Him' enable them to become stronger despite the threats of COVID-19 to their already compromised immune system. Most participants identified a number of activities which allowed them to calm their nerves and keep them straight on thinking on how to overcome the challenges the pandemic brought to them. These activities include doing recreational activities, starting to grow plants, keeping a pet, checking online courses, and

doing something productive like cooking, learning, and 'tiktoks'.

Pax H. "I pray. Sa totoo lang since nagka HIV ako feeling ko mas close na ako kay God. Nung nag ka Covid baka doble pa."

/ "games, help out sa bahay tapos siguro tiktok malaking bagay para pamparela" (I pray. Honestly, I think I became a lot closer to God when I knew I was positive, and when covid came, I think it doubled. / games, helping with house chores, and Tiktok helps a lot to relax)

Pax E. "kapit lang kay lord, ginsasabay ko sa prayers ko talaga na sana magbalik na sa normal. / naging plantita na si nana mo... nakakatabang man kaya kun igwa ka pigkabusihan"

(Stand strong... I always include in my prayers that hopefully everything will return back to normal. / I turned out to be a Plantita, it helps if you have something else to do)

Pax C. "siguro sarong bagay sa harong na nawa wara hadit ko kapag amon kami kan ido ko... dakul ngani sya videos sa socmed ko"

(I think one thing that helps me relieve stress at home is when I play with my dog. I even post a lot of his photos on my social media)

KI 1. "One thing, kun igwa ki sarong pagtubod na pwede ta angklahan kan hugot ta, makusog man su pagtubod ta. In fact, maski ako, since na shift kami sa covid dakulang bagay sako na everyday nagpapasalamat ako safe ako tapos pamilya ko."

(One thing to help us grounded is there is a strong belief or faith which can keep us stable. Personally, since I was shifted to covid response, I am every day thankful that me and my family are safe.)

“...sa mental health, dakulang tabang man na may stress reliever kita. Sabi ngani, one way to beat stress is beat the stressor, with covid na impossible ma beat, kaya dakulang tabang su may alternative kit ana activities para makatabang satuya, imbes para isip kan covid na mas mastress lang kita”

(It is helpful if we develop activities which can serve as our stress reliever for our mental health. One way to beat stress is beat the stressor, but with COVID-19, the cause of stress is impossible to beat. So, it is helpful if we find alternative means to keep our body and mind busy and away from thinking of that one that causes us to be stressed.)

At the **family level**, all participants except one shared that their family does not know about their HIV status. Being not able to openly talk about their emotions to their family members make it more difficult to figure out how they can help themselves in situations like: getting their HIV medicines, getting funds or money for their over-the-counter medications, or explain to their family why they need to ask someone to help them go to their treatment hubs in the middle of lockdown. While one participant shared that family support is very helpful in finding solutions to some of the problems. In addition, family members who know her HIV status provide extra emotional support as they understand her predicament better, than the time when her family does not know about it yet.

Pax D. “gusto ko man maaram ninda, pero dai ko mahanap su kusog ki buot sabihon.”

(I wanted to let them know. But I couldn't find the strength in me to do it)

Pax H. “Di ko kaya maaraman ninda, di pa ako ready. Kaya hanggat kaya ko, sosolohun ko ini...”

(I cannot handle it when they know about my status, I am not ready for it yet. As long as I can do it alone, I'll do it alone)

Pax A. “Aram ng partner ko tapos ki sarong kong tugang. Dakulang tabang na yaon sinda para sako”

(My partner knows, and my sibling knows too. It's of great help to me that they know my status.)

KI 2. “It is never easy talaga na magdisclose ka kang HIV status mo. In fact, dipisil ngani tanggapupin sa sadiri na positive ka. Pero, as a peer counselor, I try to empower mga PLHIV clients na to find strength to tell at least one close family member to start.”

(It is never easy to disclose your HIV status. In fact, accepting on your own that you are positive is not easy too. However, as a peer counselor, I try to empower the PLHIV clients to find strength to tell at least one close family member)

KI 1. “Pigpopromote mi talaga na importante ma establish ang support system ng PLHIVs. Lalo na nasa pandemic kita, mas kaipuhan ninda su family ninda para makatabang enkaso may remalaso baga. Lalo na kung naghehelang ngaya su PL, at least kung may kaanak an legal guardian pwede mag sya mag asikaso kan pangangaipo ni PL.”

(We are promoting to PLHIV clients to establish their support system. Especially in this time of pandemic, family support is needed. If ever the client is sick, a legal guardian can help process any legal requirements needed by the client.)

At the **level of the community**, all participants shared that they belong to a PLHIV support group except for two others. This support group is called GM plus which is the support arm of GM Bicol (or the Gentlemen Bicol for Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights, Inc. This support group allowed them access to other PLHIVs who they can seek advises and share their struggles. All the participants who shared that they are part of GM plus expressed that they have found a safe place for them which they can consider a little community which they can freely express

themselves despite of their HIV status. In the middle of pandemic, this platform allowed them to share their stories, their struggles and how to win over hurdles they are facing. This group also allowed them to connect to professionals which they can seek medical advises. GM plus also enabled them to get their voices and concerns to proper authorities.

Pax A. "Kan enot, paghuna ko mahal ang GM. Free palan sya, tapos igwa pa sinda GM plus na tatabangan ka makilala ang iba pa na PLHIV sa Bicol..." / "if may mga hapot ako, sa gc lang ng GM plus nakukuha ko na simbag sa mga bagay bagay na gusto ko masabutan"

(I though GM Bicol services are expensive. But its free. Then they have GM plus wherein they will help you meet other PLHIVs in Bicol. / If I have anything that bothers, I can just ask other members in the group chat and gets the answer I need from them)

Pax B. "Sa BRT (referring to Bicol Regional Training and Teaching Hospital) pa treatment hub ko. Sa totoo lang, may kaka-refill ko lang, pero pano ka kun mataod taod pa ini na lockdown..."

(My treatment hub is in BRT. I just got my refill, but what will happen to me if this lockdown will be extended...)

Pax G. "Pasalamat ako sa GM bicol kasi pigtabangan ako ninda maka refill meds ko. Pigtawan pa ako ninda foodpacks"

(I am thankful to GM Bicol because they helped me get medicine refills. They also gave me food assistance.)

KI 2. "GM Plus is our organization's support arm for PLHIV community. At first this group is to help them be together as we provide technical support to empower them become advocators."

"Since nag start ang lockdown, we tried to track our PLHIV members sa GM+ kung hain sinda, pira na lang medicines ninda. We helped them get their refills. Despite the lockdown, naghahanap kami means to

make sure they get their ART meds."

(Since the start of lockdown, we tracked our PLHIV members in GM+, their locations and how much more their medication stocks are. We helped them get their refills. Despite the lockdown, we try to find ways to make sure they get their refills.)

KI 1. "alam ko gm+. Nasa GC din ako nila, and often I answer their questions na related sa programs naming, sa philhealth nila, at kung ano man mga hapot ninda"
(I know GM+. I am in their group chat and often its me who answer their questions related to hiv programs, their philhealth, and other questions they have.)

One participant who isn't GM plus member shared that he got trapped in his house and no means to get his medicine refilled. Eventually found a Facebook page about HIV, and after checking the page, he was referred to check GM Bicol FB page. Doing so enabled him to connect to GM Bicol and get the proper advises he needed to help him with his concerns. GM Bicol helps PLHIVs who need refills by bridging the gap of HIV programs impacted by the pandemic.

Pax C. "may community page na may HIV posts ako na nailing, kan pigmessage ko sinda si GM bicol daa hanapon ko. / salamat sa GM Bicol nakahanap ako way maka refill"

(I was a community page with HIV posts, and when I contacted them, I was referred to GM Bicol / thanks to GM Bicol, I got my refills)

KI2. "GM Bicol is community-based group we started in 2015. Siguro medyo madami na din ang LGUs na kilala kami and even DOH region 5, pigkukua na kami na community partner para sa activities and program ninda." (GM Bicol is a community-based group we started in 2015. I trust that at this point a lot of LGUs

know us and even DOH Region 5 take our group as their community partner in their HIV programs and activities.)

“If may PLHIV new contact samuya, usually pig aaram mi su unique code ninda para ma validate kung sain na treatment hub sinda, then nag coordinate kami sa hub and sa LGU kung hain sya”

(If we get new PLHIV contacts, we usually ask for their unique code and check where treatment hub are they enrolled to, then we coordinate with their hubs and the LGUs where he/she is located.)

Another participant shared his experience while being displaced by the community quarantine. Through a friend, he got to connect with GM Bicol who operates in Bicol Region. Despite being in Laguna, he was able to get the laboratory tests he needed and get HIV medicines as well.

Pax H. “huna ko talaga sa laguna na matatapos buhay ko. Wara man ako ibang maranihan pati. Dakulang bagay na may grupo arug sa GM, na natabangan ako makakonek sa hub didi”

(I was devastated and thought I was going to die in Laguna. I was helpless and got no one to ask help from. It's a big help to find a group like GM which was able to help me be linked to the treatment hub here.)

KI 2. “GM joined a national network to assist exactly those PLHIVs who were displaced by the pandemic...”

KI 1. “katulong naming ang GM bicol at GAYON organization para facilitate concerns ng mga PLHIVs, especially now na ang HIV program government nalipat sa covid”

(GM Bicol and GAYON organization helps us to facilitate concerns of PLHIVs, especially now that HIV programs were temporarily shifted to man covid response)

participants' experiences

Adapting ecological model in public health, analysis of the lived experiences of the participants was factored in four levels: intrapersonal, interpersonal, community and public policy.

Intrapersonal. In line with intrapersonal factors, common findings were high awareness of the participants about their health condition, impact of the pandemic to their mental health, and individual lived experience of difficulty to get courage in disclosing their status to their family.

All participants are well aware of their present health condition, that they are immunocompromised. This understanding of self, enabled them to meticulously observe prescribed minimum health protocols such as wearing of protective gears, handwashing or sanitizing, and maintaining physical distance. All participants have acknowledged that their present situation is causing them some degree of anxiety and stress. This may call for both public and private groups which main focus are mental health or HIV/AIDS to provide necessary interventions.

Most participants recognized that it is emotionally difficult to let their family know about their HIV status. Which at the individual level, the person may have trouble seeking the support system a family member could provide. Hence, this may need more interventions from existing support or social groups.

Measures/Recommendation drawn from the

Figure 2. Ecological Model (Measures to be Proposed)

Interpersonal. Along interpersonal factors, three notable experiences are: family support, peer support, and support group.

One participant shared that getting a family member to provide support is very helpful. Getting a support system as strong and close as one's own family can be very helpful to a PLHIV especially in times of pandemic. While the other participants expressed that they couldn't find ways to talk openly about their HIV status to their family. This can be an area of further in-depth study, and may open opportunities to bringing same people who aren't ready to disclose their status with their family to be included in an external support group.

Most participants recognized that a support group composed of PLHIVs provided them comfort, access to information they need based of the experiences of their peers, and linkages to professional are helpful to them. In this time of lockdown, and access to usual services are halted, easy access to information is substantially helpful to PLHIVs.

Notable is the peer support from other PLHIVs.

Community. Community factors found promising are existence of active private organizations or community groups which are capable to fill in the gaps in HIV services during pandemic.

Community-based organizations (CBO) and groups providing HIV services were found to be essential in bridging thinning HIV and sexual health services. All participants shared that they got most of the help they needed through a non-government organization. This calls for community groups to scale up their initiatives. Also, this can be a model which other groups with same programs to adopt. CBOs recognized for their work, by government agencies, can efficiently provide assistance to PLHIVs in aspects of: linking them to care, assisting them to access health and social information and services, and providing mechanisms to fill in the gaps in HIV medicines refill for PLHIVs.

Public Policy. Drawn from the information gathered, and experienced of the participants on the ground, public healthy policies can be recommended, especially in institutionalizing that CBOs with active presences in communities, to be part of the health service delivery network.

Discussion

The information gathered from the participants of the study suggests that there is a need to recreate an effective and efficient system of interventions to fill in the gaps of the severely impacted health system as most LGUs and health services providers shifted its priority to responding to COVID-19 pandemic. Undeniably, the imposed lockdown or community quarantine is important element of preventing the spread of COVID-19. According to International Perspective on Sexual and Reproductive Health, sexual and reproductive health will also be affected by societal responses to the pandemic, such as local or national lockdowns that force health services to shut down if they are not deemed essential, as well as the consequences of physical distancing, travel restrictions and economic slowdowns (Riley T., Sully E., Ahmed Z., and Biddlecom A. 2020).

Despite the implementation of travel restrictions and community quarantines, health programs especially services for PLHIVs should not be neglected in the process. PLHIVs rely on their HIV medicines, which are often referred to as life-saving

medications to most PLHIVs. A person with HIV is already immunocompromised, and these HIV drugs keeps them to their maximum health possible. ART is a combination of antiretroviral drugs and other medications to prevent and treat the many opportunistic infections that a PLHIV may manifest when the immune system becomes compromised due to HIV (UNAIDS 2016 and WHO 2015). A number of opportunities to improve the health and living conditions of PLHIVs amid pandemic. These opportunities include: creating and improving support system for PLHIVs, engaging communities towards public decision-making and social responsibility, and maximizing CSO and CBO presence in delivery of HIV programs and services. According to UNAIDS, when communities organize and people empower each other, oppression can be replaced by rights and access to HIV services can be accelerated, and that community leadership in the HIV and AIDS response helps to ensure that HIV services are relevant to, and reach, the people who need them the most (UNAIDS 2019). In addition, based on reports by UNAIDS, CSOs and community-based organizations (CBOs) play a pivotal role in reshaping the HIV programming in communities affected by the pandemic (UNAIDS 2020).

The experience of PLHIVs who were displaced and locked down by the imposed community quarantine also suggests that government sexual health and HIV programs were made efficient in delivering its purpose with the presence of active CBO in service delivery network. This CSO/CBO and government working together to address gaps in HIV programming amid pandemic is a promising model which can be institutionalized for sustainability. Looking back, even before the pandemic, HIV/AIDS services and programming has been lacking. Current country efforts have been insufficient to reach targets on testing, diagnosis, and antiretroviral therapy initiation and that the HIV situation of country reflects the need to have an increased resource allocation and programmatic enhancements, however, civil society organizations can provide support to

bridge gaps in government HIV programming and services (DOH 2016 and UNAIDS 2020).

Presence of support group under the management of a CBO added value to improving the state of living conditions of PLHIVs during the episodes of strict lockdowns. The services PLHIVs received from a support group are access to information, access to counseling, access to peers, and extended to getting financial and food assistance, and assistance to get ART medication refills. These services are essentially what a primary healthcare point of contact can provide in normal days, however, amidst pandemic, these basic health services are difficult to find. According to UNICEF and the WHO, community-based health care is an essential part of primary care at all times; in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, the distinct capacity of trusted community members for social engagement and delivering care where it is needed is ever more critical (WHO 2020).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings of the study reflect the lived experiences of the PLHIVs in Bicol Region affected by the COVID-19 imposed protocols, and points towards possible measures to fill in the gaps on the severely impacted HIV/AIDS and sexual healthcare system due to shift to COVID-19 response. Point of actions to improved the state of living conditions of PLHIVs along the lines of their health needs can be geared towards the following dimensions: intrapersonal factors, interpersonal factors, community factors, and public policy.

Intrapersonal dimensions may include conduct of educational discussions to provide PLHIVs skills and helpful information along the lines of mental health, COVID-19 and the PLHIV community, finding a support group, and developing a personal ritual to improve relationship to self. Along interpersonal factors, CBOs and LGUs can work together in sustaining existing support groups, providing technical assistance to its managers, providing capacity-building opportunities for PLHIVs, and other training and education opportunities which can lead to empowerment

and leadership. Strengthening community factors may include mapping of CBOs and CSOs with HIV program and harmonizing their efforts, looking into their current level of capacity and providing necessary technical assistance to strengthen their existing programs. Most importantly, along the dimension of public policy, is to sustain good practices by GM Bicol in Region 5, and institutionalization of membership of the active CBOs to the existing HIV and healthcare service delivery network. In addition, for LGUs to enact policy support to delivery of HIV programs and services, which may include: transport services for PLHIVs to ensure access to ART drugs, and; for provincial level LGUs, to support establishment of social hygiene clinics or treatment hubs in their respective geo-political areas.

This study focused solely on the situation of PLHIVs in Bicol region, specifically, information about their lived experiences amid pandemic during the three months of series of lockdowns. Future researchers may look into the side of service providers and HIV program implementation. Further study can also be done from the perspective of CBOs providing HIV programs and services amid pandemic.

References

WHO (2020), "Maintaining essential health services: operational guidance for the COVID-19 context interim guidance", retrieved on May 5, 2020 from <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-2019-nCoV-essential-health-services-2020.1>

Tomacruz (2020), "Duterte places Luzon on lockdown to battle coronavirus" retrieved on May 5, 2020 from <https://www.rappler.com/nation/luzon-total-lockdown-battle-coronavirus-outbreak>

HIV.gov (2019), "HIV Treatment Overview" retrieved on May 5, 2020 from <https://www.hiv.gov/hiv-basics/staying-in-hiv-care/hiv-treatment/hiv-treatment-overview>

National HIV/AIDS & STI Surveillance and Strategic Information Unit - NHSSS (2020), "HIV/AIDS & ART Registry of the Philippines January-March 2020 report", Epidemiology Bureau, Department of Health, City of Manila, Philippines

DOH CHD Bicol (2019), "2019 Year-end Report", 2019 Stakeholders Meeting, Legazpi City, Philippines

DOH (2018), "Updated list of DOH-designated HIV treatment hubs and primary HIV care facilities", Department Memorandum No. 2018-0031, Department of Health, City of Manila, Philippines

UNAIDS (2016), "Get on the fast track", UNAIDS Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS, Geneva, Switzerland

WHO (2015), "Guideline on when to start antiretroviral therapy and on pre-exposure prophylaxis for HIV" retrieved on May 9, 2021

from <https://www.euro.who.int/en/publications/abstracts/guideline-on-when-to-start-antiretroviral-therapy-and-on-pre-exposure-prophylaxis-for-hiv-2015>

UNAIDS (2019), "UNAIDS Data 2019", UNAIDS Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS, Geneva, Switzerland

UNAIDS (2020), "Ensuring that people living with HIV in the Philippines have access to treatment during COVID-19" retrieved

on May 9, 2021 from https://www.unaids.org/en/resources/presscentre/featurestories/2020/april/20200408_philippines

DOH (2016) "The state of the Philippine HIV Epidemic 2016", Department of Health – Epidemiology Bureau, City of Manila, Philippines

Quintalang M.I., Bermudez A., and Operario D. (2020), Reimagining the Future of HIV Service Implementation in the Philippines Based on Lessons from COVID-19" retrieved on May 29, 2020 from

<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10461-020-02934-x>

Riley T., Sully E., Ahmed Z., and Biddlecom A. (2020), "Estimates of the Potential Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Sexual and Reproductive Health in Low- and Middle-Income Countries" retrieved on May 29, 2020 from <https://www.guttmacher.org/journals/ipsrh/2020/04/estimates-potential-impact-covid-19-pandemic-sexual-and-reproductive-health>

WHO (2020), "COVID-19 significantly impacts health services for noncommunicable diseases" retrieved June 14, 2020 from

<https://www.who.int/news/item/01-06-2020-covid-19-significantly-impacts-health-services-for-noncommunicable-diseases>

WHO (2020), "Community-based health care, including outreach and campaigns, in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic", Interim Guidance May 2020, World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland

McLeroy, K. R., Bibeau, D., Steckler, A., &

Glanz, K. (1988). "An Ecological Perspective on Health Promotion Programs. Health Education & Behavior, 15(4)", retrieved on June 15, 2020 from <https://doi.org/10.1177/109019818801500401>